

A study on adverse effects induced by chemotherapy drugs used for colorectal cancer and their management in Nepal cancer hospital and research center

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Abstract: Aim: To study the prevalence of adverse effects when chemotherapy is administered in colorectal cancer and the management of reported ADR. Methodology: This was a retrospective observational study conducted in Nepal Cancer Hospital and Research Centre visited from January 2020 to December 2021 for treatment of colorectal cancer. The patient who met the study criteria were enrolled in the study and the data were collected from their case records. Management given to the patient was recorded. Results: A total of 90 patients received chemotherapy, out of which 81 (90%) reported ADR. 5FU/LV, FOLFOX, CAPOX, and Oral capecitabine were administered as adjuvant therapy and FOLFORI as palliative. There were 381 ADRs reported in 81 patients. Infection (55.6%) and Diarrhea (51.9%) were the most prevalent ADRs. The older population showed more ADR compared to the younger ($P=0.05$) and oral capecitabine reported less ADR compared to another chemo regimen. Diarrhea and Sepsis accounted for most of the severe ADR requiring prolonged hospitalization. Most of the ADRs were managed Symptomatically and only in severe or hypersensitivity cases the chemotherapy regimen was changed or stopped. Conclusion: The results of the study reveal the hat most prevalent ADR is an infection (myelosuppression) and diarrhea. Severe Diarrhea and Sepsis were the most common cause of prolonged hospital stay. Most of the ADRs were resolved symptomatically in clinical care.

Keywords: Chemotherapy, ADRs, Management of ADRs

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Introduction

Colorectal Cancer (CRC) is the third most common malignancy and the second leading cause of death globally (1). Around 40% of patients who present with CRC will progress to metastatic disease and eventually die from this malignancy (1). Although anti-cancer drugs are well studied and highly beneficial for better treatment outcomes when compared to other classes of medications, they are more associated with ADRs (2). The adverse effects of chemotherapy are often an unobserved clinical obstacle in cancer management (3). The ADRs associated with anticancer agents are common and may be enhanced when the drugs are used in combinations (4). According to the National Cancer Registry of Nepal, adverse reactions caused by chemotherapy affect patients' work & family life. In Nepal, antineoplastic agents are frequently associated with several ADRs. ADRs associated with chemotherapy have considerable economic as well as clinical costs as they often lead to hospital admission, prolongation of hospital stay, and emergency department visits. Sometimes the ADRs may be critical and severe and the cost needed to treat could be more than the cost needed to treat the actual condition itself (5).

The healthcare providers involved in the management of a cancer patient have to play a great role in the detection, monitoring, and prevention of ADRs to provide better pharmaceutical care to patients. One of the management of side effects includes a reduction in the dose intensity of chemotherapy. However, there is evidence suggesting patients who receive a low dose of chemotherapy have reduced survival rates (6). In other cases, alterations in drug therapy have been shown to reduce adverse effects. Despite its importance, there is a lack of research on the prevalence of types of ADRs in Nepal and their management.

Research Methodology

A retrospective study was conducted in Nepal Cancer Hospital and Research Center (NCHRC), Harrisiddhi, Nepal. Site approval was obtained from the Department of Medical Record of NCHRC, Harrisiddhi. Data Collection was done from May 2022 to June 2022.

Medical records of all the hospitalized CRC patients, who had received chemotherapy from January 2020 to December 2021 were reviewed. Files of patients diagnosed with CRC were separated and relevant and necessary data were collected from Patient Clinical Note, Discharge Summary, Day Care Admission Form, Common Toxicity Criteria, Cardiac Notes, Lab Reports, and Medication Cardex.

For each patient, the following data were recorded: age, sex, co-morbidity, initial complaints, diagnosis, date of chemotherapy started, medications prescribed in addition to chemo, chemo regimen used throughout treatment, ADRs reported, date of ADRs reported, management of reported ADRs, laboratory values/finding and information about emergency care required for serious ADRs. ADRs which required emergency care or prolonged stay were identified as severe ADRs. Statistical Analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28.0 by International Business Machine Corporation (IBM), Armonk, New York. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics namely mean with standard deviation for continuous variables and number with percentage for categorical variables. The independent variable (Demographics and Chemo Regimen) was determined using the chi-square test (X^2) at a significance of 5%. P-value of <0.05 was considered a statistically significant

Results

There were a total of 2631 diagnosed cases of cancer from January 2020 to December 2021. Ca Breast has the highest prevalence rate (7.4%) among cancer-diagnosed patients, followed by Ca Lungs (6.1%) and then Ca Colorectal (4.3%) among diagnosed cancer cases.

Table 1: Prevalence of Cancer in NCHRC

Variable	Frequency(n)	Prevalence Rate %
Total Patient Visit from Jan 2020-Dec 2021	4614	
Types of Cancer		
CA Breast	342	7.4
CA Lungs	281	6.1
CA Colorectal	197	4.3
CA Cervix	178	3.9
CA Stomach	146	3.2
CA Ovary	101	2.2
CA Thyroid	84	1.8
CA Gall Bladder	83	1.8
CA Pancreas	73	1.6
CA Tongue	71	1.5
CA Prostate	55	1.2
Others Cancer	1020	

A total of 90 patients received chemotherapy for treatment of CRC in Nepal Cancer Hospital and Research Centre during the study period. In this patient group, 57.8% were males and 42.2% were females. A total of 30% of the patients who received chemotherapy were less than 45 years old whereas 70% of patients were older than 45 of age. The **mean age was 54.41 ± 16.8 years**. The youngest to receive chemotherapy was 19 years and the oldest receiving chemotherapy was 94 years old. Out of 90 patients, 5 (5.55%) patients died during the treatment procedure.

Table 2: Patient demographics who received chemotherapy in NCHRC for CRC

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
18-25	7	7.8
26-35	9	10.0
36-45	11	12.2
46-55	15	16.7
56-65	27	30.0
66 and above	21	23.3

Gender		
Male	52	57.8
Female	38	42.2

Table 3: Diagnosis and Chemo regimens used in the treatment of CRC

Variable	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)	
Diagnosis			
CA Rectum	54	60.0	
CA Colon	28	31.1	
CA Rectum Metastasis	6	6.7	
CA Colon Metastasis	2	2.2	
Chemotherapy Regimen			
Mono Regimen	65	72.2	
Combination Regimen	25	27.8	
Regimen	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)	Percent of Cases (%)
5-FU/LV	16	13.1	17.8
FOLFOX	40	32.8	44.4
CAPOX	24	19.7	26.7
FOLFIRI	11	9.0	12.2
Oral Capecitabine	28	23.0	31.1
Others (FU + Mitomycin)	3	2.5	3.3

Table 4: Types of ADRs reported

ADRs			
Yes	81	90	

No	9	10	
Types of ADRs Observed			Percent of Cases (%)
Nausea	25		30.9
Vomiting	26		32.1
Weakness	25		30.9
Anorexia	27		33.3
Constipation	9		11.1
Diarrhea	42		51.9
Allergic Reaction/HSR	20		24.7
Burning Micturition	14		17.3
Infection	45		55.6
Brady/Tachycardia	5		6.2
Sepsis	9		11.1
Hypo/Hypertension	17		21.0
Abdominal Pain	25		30.9
Neuropathy	21		25.9
Anemia	18		22.2
Mucositis	4		4.9

A total of 81 (90%) patients reported adverse effects due to the administration of chemotherapy. Of all the ADRs reported the most common ADRs reported were infection (55.6%) and diarrhea (51.9%). Nausea and vomiting were reported in 30.9% and 32.1% of the patients respectively. Anorexia (33.3%), weakness (30.9%), abdominal pain (30.9%), neuropathy (25.9%), and HSR (24.7%) were some of the notable ADRs reported. There was a total of 381 ADRs reported in 81 patients.

Table 5: Association of the demographic and treatment regimen with ADRs

Variable	Adverse Reaction		P * value
Gender	Yes (N=81 (%))	No (N=9 (%))	
Male	47 (58)	5 (55.5)	0.887
Female	34 (41.9)	4 (44.4)	
Age (Years)	Yes (N=81 (%))	No (N=9 (%))	
<=25	6 (7.4)	1 (11.1)	0.05
26-35	5 (6.2)	4 (44.4)	
36-45	9 (11.1)	2 (22.2)	
46-55	14 (17.3)	1 (11.1)	
56-65	27 (33.3)	0 (0)	
>66	20 (24.7)	1 (11.1)	
Chemo Regimen	Yes (N=104 (%))	No (N=18 (%))	
FU/LV	15 (14.4)	1 (5.6)	0.01
FOLFOX	39 (37.5)	1 (5.6)	
CAPOX	22 (21.2)	2 (11.1)	
FOLFIRI	10 (9.6)	1 (5.6)	
Oral Capecitabine	15 (14.4)	13 (72.2)	
Others (FU + Mitomycin)	3 (2.9)	0 (0)	

Table 6: Association of the treatment regimens with reported ADR

Variable	Treatment Regimen					P*Value
ADR Reported	5-FU/LV	FOLFOX	CAPOX	FOLFIRI	Capecitabine	
Nausea						
Yes (%)	5 (19.2)	11 (42.3)	7(26.9)	2(7.7)	1(3.8)	0.096
No (%)	11 (11.8)	29(31.2)	17(18.3)	9(9.7)	27(29)	
Vomiting						

Yes (%)	5(20)	11(44)	5(20)	2(8)	2(8)	0.256
No (%)	11(11.7)	29(30.9)	19(20.2)	9(9.6)	26(27.7)	
Weakness						
Yes (%)	8(29.6)	10(37)	1(3.7)	4(14.8)	4(14.8)	0.008*
No (%)	8(8.7)	30(32.6)	23(25)	7(7.6)	24(26.1)	
Anorexia						
Yes (%)	5(19.2)	8(30.8)	6(23.1)	2(7.7)	5(19.2)	0.845
No (%)	11(11.8)	32(34.4)	18(19.4)	9(9.7)	23(24.7)	
Constipation						
Yes (%)	2(22.2)	3(33.3)	1(11.1)	0	3(33.3)	0.690
No (%)	14(12.7)	37(33.6)	23(20.9)	11(10)	25(22.7)	
Diarrhea						
Yes (%)	9(20.5)	18(40.9)	7(15.9)	3(6.8)	7(15.9)	0.168
No (%)	7(9.3)	22(29.3)	17(22.7)	8(10.7)	21(28)	
Allergic Reaction/HSR						
Yes (%)	3(15)	7(35)	2(10)	4(20)	4(20)	0.351
No (%)	13(13.1)	33(33.3)	22(22.2)	7(7.1)	24(24.2)	
Burning Micturition						
Yes (%)	5 (38.5)	4 (30.8)	0	0	4(38.5)	0.022
No (%)	11(10.4)	36 (34)	24(22.6)	11(10.4)	24(22.6)	
Infection						
Yes (%)	7(15.2)	19(41.3)	10(21.7)	5(10.9)	5(10.9)	0.141
No (%)	9(12.3)	21(28.8)	14(19.2)	6(8.2)	23(31.5)	
Brady/Tachycardia						
Yes (%)	0	2(40)	2(40)	1(20)	0	0.453
No (%)	16(14)	38(33.3)	22(19.3)	10(8.8)	28(24.6)	
Sepsis						
Yes (%)	1(11.1)	5(55.6)	1(11.1)	2(22.2)	0	0.207
No (%)	15(13.5)	36(32.4)	21(18.9)	11(9.9)	28(25.2)	

Hypo/Hypertension						
Yes (%)	1(5.6)	8(44.4)	3(16.7)	1(5.6)	5(27.8)	0.676
No (%)	15(14.9)	32(31.7)	21(20.8)	10(9.9)	23(22.8)	
Abdominal Pain						
Yes (%)	6(23.1)	7(26.9)	4(15.4)	2(7.7)	7(26.9)	0.499
No (%)	10(10.8)	33(35.5)	20(21.5)	9(9.7)	21(22.6)	
Neuropathy						
Yes (%)	0	18(85.7)	3(14.3)	0	0	0.03*
No (%)	16(16.3)	22(22.4)	21(21.4)	11(11.2)	28(28.6)	
Anemia						
Yes (%)	2(10.5)	9(47.4)	5(26.3)	1(5.3)	2(10.5)	0.426
No (%)	14(14)	31(31)	19(19)	10(10)	26(26)	
Mucositis						
Yes (%)	4(100)	0	0	0	0	0.04*
No (%)	12(10.4)	40(34.8)	24(20.9)	11(9.6)	28(24.3)	

Severe ADRs reported:

The severity of ADR was assessed by comparing the hospitalization period and emergency assessment required. ADRs that prolonged the hospitalization period and life-threatening requiring emergency assessment were identified as severe ADRs. 31

Table 7: Severe ADRs Reported (N=51)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Severe ADR Reported	31	38.2
Mild/Moderate ADR Reported	50	61.7

Figure 2: Frequency of Reported Severe ADRs.

Figure 2: Type of Management for reported ADRs

Table 8: Management of different reported ADRs.

Variable	Frequency (n)	Management					
		No Management (n)	Symptomatic Management (n)	Chemo on Hold (n)	Dose Reduction (n)	Regimen Changed (n)	Stopped Chemo (n)
ADR Reported							

Nausea*(%)	25	3(12.0)	19(76.0)	2(8.0)	0	2(8.0)	0
Vomiting*(%)	26	0	25(96.2)	2(7.7)	0	1(3.8)	2(7.7)
Weakness*(%)	25	9(36.0)	10(40.0)	2(8.0)	3(12.0)	1(4.0)	1(4.0)
Anorexia (%)	27	16(59.3)	8(29.6)	2(7.4)	1(3.7)	0	0
Constipation (%)	9	0	7(77.8)	1(11.1)	0	0	1(11.1)
Diarrhea*(%)	42	4(9.5)	35(83.3)	6(14.3)	0	1(2.4)	1(2.4)
Allergic Reaction*(%)	20	4(20)	14(70)	3(15)	0	3(15)	2(10)
Burning Micturition*(%)	14	2(14.3)	11(78.6)	2(14.3)	0	0	0
Infection (%)	45	7(15.2)	34(73.9)	4(8.7)	8(17.4)	0	0
Brady/Tachycardia (%)	5	0	4(80)	1(20)	0	0	0
Sepsis*(%)	9	0	6(66.7)	6(66.7)	1(11.1)	1(11.1)	1(11.1)
Hypo/Hypertension (%)	17	2(11.8)	15(88.2)	0	0	0	0
Abdominal Pain*(%)	25	4(4.3)	24(85.7)	0	0	0	2(7.1)
Neuropathy*(%)	21	0	21(100)	1(4.7)	1(4.7)	1(4.7)	1(4.7)
Anemia*(%)	18	9(50)	8(44.4)	2(11.1)	1(5.6)	0	0
Mucositis (%)	4	0	4(100)	0	0	0	0

Most of the ADRs were managed symptomatically. Chemotherapy was stopped when the patient was intolerant to chemo. During Sepsis Chemo was kept on hold or stopped. Sepsis management required prolonged hospital stay as several different side effects were seen from diarrhea to abnormal rhythm. If ADRs reported were mild such as mild nausea, mild diarrhea, and mild allergic reaction there was no intervention made.

ADRs Reported	Symptomatic Management	
	Initial Management	Additional
Nausea and Vomiting	Perinorm 10mg, Domperidone 10mg	Aprepitant 125/80/80mg
Diarrhea	Metronidazole DF Loperamide 4mg (2tablets)	ORS, Ciprofloxacin 500mg, Potassium Chloride, Aerozyme
Constipation	Ezivac Enema	Water Enema, Bisacodyl 10mg

Myelosuppression	Amoxicillin and Clavulanic acid (500mg+125mg), Levofloxacin 500mg	IV Filgrastim 300 mg
Neuropathy	Pregabalin 75mg, Methyl cobalamin 1500mg	
Burning Micturition	Flavoxate 200mg	
Anorexia	Lysine + Cyproheptadine (2TSF)	
Weakness	Glutaspent 1 Sachet, Siligreen G 1 Sachet, Protein Supplements	
Hypersensitivity Reaction	Fexofenadine hydrochloride 180mg	IV Pheniramine Maleate, IV Hydrocortisone
Abdominal Pain	Hyoscine 10mg or 20mg	
Anemia	Ferrous Ascorbate 100mg	
Mucositis	Clotrimazole, Choline Salicylate	

Table 9 shows medication administered for the management of different ADRs in NCHRC. Initial management is a medication given according to protocols of NCHRC whereas additional are those medications given to the patient according to the condition of the patient.

Discussion

In this study, 81(90%) patients out of 90 showed ADRs during chemotherapy. This study found no association between gender and adverse reactions ($P=0.887$). More number of elderly patients were more prone to ADRs than younger patients. The elderly age group is more susceptible to ADRs and hence requires more monitoring for the ADRs (9).

Different chemotherapy regimens are used in CRC treatment. The regimen used for the treatment of CRC are FOLFOX, CAPOX, FOLFIRI, and 5FU/LV (7). FOLFOX and 5FU/LV are used as the main adjuvant chemotherapy in patients and FOLFIRI is used as palliative chemotherapy. CAPOX was mainly used as a substitution for FOLFOX when ADRs were reported. During the study period, the unavailability of 5FU due to the COVID-19 pandemic led to the use of CAPOX instead of FOLFOX in some patients as initial treatment. CAPOX is as effective as FOLFOX as adjuvant therapy for CRC and each regimen have similar side effect as both regimes consist of Oxaliplatin and 5-FU, one in IV form whereas the other in oral pro-drug form (9) (10). There were more ADRs reported in the IV form regimen compared to oral capecitabine. It could be said that oral capecitabine is more favorable in therapy requiring monotherapy of 5FU (5FU/LV) (22).

The most prevalent ADRs were infection (neutropenia, thrombocytopenia, leukopenia) (55.6%) followed by diarrhea (51.9%), anorexia (33.3%), vomiting (32.1%), nausea (30.9%), weakness (30.9%) (11) (9) (14). Nausea is more common and severe than vomiting in recent years (22) (21) however, in this study the prevalence of nausea and vomiting in the study population is similar. Infection and diarrhea were prevalent in a higher percentage and have no association with chemotherapy regimens (0.141 & 0.168 respectively) as all the regimens had higher chances of infection and diarrhea (9-19). Cancer patients are generally immunocompromised due to the administration of chemotherapy, use of corticosteroids, radiotherapy, or impairment of normal leukocyte function due to cancer. Neutropenia is probably the most important factor predisposing to infection in cancer patients (23). Infection and diarrhea account for more than 40% of severe ADRs that had been reported. It is important to monitor infections as they can lead to febrile neutropenia which in turn can lead to sepsis that can be life-threatening for the patients (21).

Diarrhea causes depletion of fluids and electrolytes, malnutrition, and hospitalization, all of which can lead to severe consequences such as a cardiovascular compromise or even death. In addition, diarrhea can interfere with and detract patients from cancer treatment by causing dosing delays or reductions in chemotherapy dose which prolongs the treatment duration and impacts survival (24). Thus, monitoring and management of ADR are important as unmanaged ADR can result in severe ADR which can be life-threatening.

Another important ADR that was noted is neuropathy; there was a strong association between neuropathy with the regimen. A regimen containing Oxaliplatin, i.e., FOLFOX and CAPOX have reported causing neuropathy. Oxaliplatin is known to be neurotoxic and oxaliplatin-induced peripheral neuropathy remains a limiting factor as it can last for months and include pain, numbness, and dysesthesias that lead to reduced quality of life and function (25). Among 39 patients who received the FOLFOX regimen, 21 patients (53.8%) developed peripheral neuropathy which in most of the patients was reoccurring in consecutive chemo cycles. Pachman et al (2015) (15) state that with each cycle of chemotherapy the severity of neuropathy increases from mild to moderate to severe. Consecutive chemo cycle treatment can increase the chances of neuropathy which can alter chemotherapy dose and duration.

Chemotherapy sometimes is associated with allergic reactions here 20 (24.3%) patients showed HSR out of which 4 were severe and caused by intolerance to Oxaliplatin. Out of 56 patients who were administered Oxaliplatin, 4 (7.14%) developed severe HSR to oxaliplatin leading to regimen change or completely stopping chemotherapy for the patient. Parel et al. (2014) (16) found that around 8.9% of patients developed hypersensitivity reactions to oxaliplatin. A limited number of chemotherapeutic agents is to be found effective for the management of CRC which again might be required to be withdrawn due to HSR, thereby reducing the number of therapeutic options (15).

Hyperglycemia is one of the severe ADRs reported commonly associated with diabetic patient and has caused prolonged stays in CRC patients. There is evidence that pre-disposing co-morbidity (diabetes) can increase the resistance to chemotherapy in patients making treatment with oxaliplatin and 5FU less effective (26). Several chemotherapy agents and corticosteroids administered to cancer patients have been associated with a risk of elevating hyperglycemia in patients (27). Diabetes patients undergoing chemotherapy prioritize their cancer treatment over managing their diabetes which causes poor glycemic control in them (28). Patients with diabetes receiving chemotherapy have an increased risk of developing glycemic issues because of increased insulin resistance, diminished insulin secretion, and exaggerated hepatic glucose output which increases the risk of having a chemotherapy reduction or stoppage.

Most of the adverse events were managed symptomatically. Sometimes instead of adding drugs, chemotherapy was kept on hold and later continued as ADRs resolved. This method has been effective for mild and moderate ADRs reported. Dose reduction was mainly done in neutropenia and a change in regimen was recommended in HSR. Chemotherapy was stopped when conditions were severe. ADRs reported altered dosage and can lead to changes in regimen prolonging the duration of treatment. Diarrhea is one of the common ADRs reported. Among 42 patients who reported diarrhea, 35 patients received Loperamide and Metronidazole for diarrhea management. Severe diarrhea was managed by ORS and IV antibiotics and loperamide as well. Octreotide was more effective than the standard dose of loperamide for the initial treatment of diarrhea (29). However, loperamide dosing was relatively low, and given the high cost of octreotide and the general effectiveness of loperamide when administered at therapeutic doses, octreotide is generally reserved as second-line therapy for patients who do not respond to high-dose loperamide.

Infection is one of the common adverse effects seen that is mainly due to neutropenia and is managed by antibiotics and administration of filgrastim. Weekly CBC is important in chemotherapy-administered patients. Neutropenia cannot always be prevented; however, tactics such as monitoring CBC weekly, checking for occult infections such as in the urinary tract or skin infection before therapy, and reducing chemotherapy drug dose in patients previously found to be extremely sensitive to these agents may help reduce the occurrence of neutropenia (30). Management of neutropenia is very important as it can lead to systemic infection and sepsis, which can delay treatment in CRC patients

and the worst-case scenario death of the patient. Management for Neutropenia was done by broad spectrum antibiotic and in case of low ANC hematopoietic growth factors (filgrastim) were administered. Any patient receiving chemotherapy who has a fever associated with neutropenia should be regarded as a “medical emergency” as it could lead to sepsis. Although filgrastim can increase neutrophil count but therapy with filgrastim has an increased chance of bone pain and headache (20). Thus, for the management of neutropenia (infection) regular monitoring of CBC and antibiotics such as a combination of Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid has been administered. Filgrastim was only administered when the ANC count was less than 1500.

Neuropathy although not severe but is one of the common and regimen-related side effects. Methylcobalamin and pregabalin an effective medication for neuropathic pain. The patient who showed neuropathy signs and pain was administered pregabalin and methylcobalamin. First-line therapy is monotherapy of gabapentinoid for management of neuropathy pain and combination therapy is regarded as second-line therapy.

HSR is another ADR that is rare but has a serious impact as it can cause a change in the chemotherapy regimen or completely stop chemotherapy. For mild to moderate HSR antihistamine has been administered but severe HSR desensitization was done according to protocol. Recommended that skin testing should be done when a platinum drug such as oxaliplatin is administered and if positive, desensitization protocol should be followed (31).

Management of ADRs due to chemotherapy is important as the ADRs can not only affect the QOL of the patient and increase the financial burden, it can affect the treatment effectiveness and duration. Proper management of ADRs has increased the efficacy of chemotherapy.

Limitations

The results of this study must be interpreted cautiously considering many important limitations; the study was single-centric, small sample size, and was carried out retrospectively. There could be missing ADRs reported in case files of the patient which were seen during the treatment. Confirmation Bias is also a limitation of the study. Missing files have lowered the number of data that could have been collected.

Conclusion

The present study showed adverse reactions and their association with gender and regimen. There are higher chances of ADRs when chemo drug is administered to CRC patients. The most common ADRs were found to be infection and diarrhea. Neuropathy was associated with regimen FOLFOX and CAPOX highlighting the fact that oxaliplatin administration has a high probability of causing neuropathy. Hypersensitivity reaction, though low incidence would limit the option for treatment regimen.

As ADR is inevitable while administering chemotherapy healthcare professionals should be careful and alert. ADRs cause an increase in the duration of treatment and also the duration of hospitalization for the management of reported ADRs. A common method of management of ADRs is symptomatic management. Chemotherapy is kept on hold in severe cases. Dose reduction is done mostly in infection and the regimen is changed in hypersensitivity. In addition, proper monitoring can help to reduce the severity of adverse effects through early detection. This highlights the need for proper counseling and monitoring of ADRs which can improve QOL and financial burden due to prolonged hospitalization due to chemotherapy-induced ADRs.

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